

Introduction of a New Chaining Method between Reactor Core and Fuel Cycle Simulations Tools with an application to Plutonium Multi-Recycling in Pressurised Water Reactors

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a new chaining method between full core and fuel cycle simulations, focusing on the introduction of a specific multi-recycling fuel, called MIX (for MOX fuel with enriched uranium support), in an EPR reactor. The chaining method relies on the use of surrogate models, here gaussian processes, to predict core performances from full core calculations for a given fuel composition given by the fuel cycle simulation. To assess the potential of this new chaining method, this paper proposes first to evaluate, then to optimise a previously presented MIX fuel deployment scenario. Thanks to the new chaining method, this work concludes on a new, consolidated, and less conservative deployment trajectory for the multi-recycling of plutonium with MIX fuel.

Keywords: fuel cycle simulation, plutonium multi-recycling, pressurised water reactor, full core calculations, gaussian processes

1. INTRODUCTION

The French government adopted in its last pluriannual energy plan, dating 2019, a new management policy for nuclear fuel in pressurised water reactors (PWR) [1]. It aims at demonstrate the viability of new fuel concepts able to manage successive recycling of the plutonium issued from PWR spent fuel. This process relies on plutonium multi-recycling in PWR. To be operable, these advanced fuels have to meet several requirements such as nuclear safety, economics and allows the plutonium and spent fuel inventory stabilisation. Furthermore, to find the best compromise within a large multiparametric space needs an optimisation process, both at the reactor core and the fuel cycle scale, to meet the targeted requisites. To do so, new optimisation methods that incorporate both core and fuel cycle calculations ought to be introduced.

Previous work on optimising the fuel cycle exists in the literature [2], where simulated fuel cycles are optimised through fuel cycle scale criteria, such as the natural uranium consumption or the quantity of high-level waste production. New methods relying on surrogate models (here neural networks) to assess fuel composition based on core calculations exist [3][4], as well as studies on how the fuel cycle can influence the design of a reactor, in this example a sodium fast reactor [5].

However here, the main difference is that the paradigm is reversed, hence it is the reactor design that influences the fuel cycle. Because the reactor design is already set, only few latitudes exists regarding fuel fabrication due to the "early" deployment of plutonium multi-recycling in PWR, therefore fuel management in PWR remains the last optimisation lever available.

This work presents a new chaining method between core and fuel cycle simulations. It focuses on the introduction of the specific multi-recycling fuel, called MIX (a MOX fuel with enriched uranium support)

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dedicated to plutonium multi-recycling in an EPR reactor, fully loaded with it. MIX fuel radial description and EPR core loading pattern are detailed in Figure 1. The evolution of the French nuclear fleet in the coming decades is simulated by the EDF nuclear fuel cycle simulation tool TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE [6]. This tool returns for each year of the scenario specific fuel assembly fuel enrichments and plutonium isotopic composition vector. Data returned from the simulations then becomes inputs variables for PWR core calculations, based on the CEA spectral code APOLLO2 [7], and the EDF core simulation code COCAGNE [8]. TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE and COCAGNE have different computing costs, respectively 1 minute vs. 1 hour. To avoid a strict chaining between the two codes and to ease the evaluation process of the reactor cores, a database is built from core calculations, and surrogate models are trained onto it. Surrogate models are based on gaussian processes [9] and database construction is derived from previous works for PWR applications [10].

Figure 1. MIX fuel and fuel management description.

For the first time, this new chaining method allows to directly introduce reactor core observables such as the power peak factor or the voiding reactivity effect into nuclear fuel studies, aiming to deepen both their robustness and reliability.

In order to assess the potential of this new chaining method, this paper proposes to evaluate a previously presented nuclear scenario that demonstrates the stabilisation of the plutonium inventory through the introduction of the MIX fuel in a possible future French EPR fleet [11]. After an introduction of the chaining method, of both the calculation scheme and the surrogate models construction, this paper presents the scenario of application and discuss how MIX fuel composition impact optimisation targets and is limited by core constraints. Optimisation work on the MIX fuel composition is then performed. Thanks to the new chaining method, this work finally concludes on in a new, consolidated, and less conservative scenario trajectory for the multi-recycling of plutonium with MIX fuel batches.

2. METHOD

This work introduces a new chaining between neutronics and fuel cycle simulation codes that permits to extract quantities of interest from core calculations while working on fuel cycle studies. The connexion between the reactor and the fuel cycle scale is done thanks to surrogate models, here gaussian process. This section first discusses the chaining method then details the surrogate models construction.

2.1. General Overview

The chaining method is introduced to validate fuel cycle simulations both from the fuel cycle and the core neutronics point of view. Figure 2 below illustrates the proposed chaining method.

Figure 2. Chaining method synoptic.

It describes as follow: fuel data are extracted from a fuel cycle simulated with TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE. These fuel data feed the design of experiments, giving its range of variation, and the surrogate models creation. The use of surrogate models instead of direct calculations permit to reduce the computing time between different scenario validation steps, the chaining method being inherently interactive. Each year of the simulation, core performances are estimated thanks to surrogate models following the initial TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE proposition. If the proposed scenario is acceptable from both core and fuel cycle criteria, it is then validated. If no, surrogate models are used for the search of alternative plutonium contents and U-235 fuel enrichments, and an alternative scenario is proposed to validation.

2.2. Surrogate Models Construction

As introduced in Section 2.1, surrogate models are used to reduce the computing time of the iterative chaining method and to allow large objective spaces exploration.

Here the two optimisation objectives are the minimisation of both the peaking factor, defined here as the ratio between the fuel pin power over the pin mean power, and of the fuel front-end cost, a simplified economics indicator, being the ratio between the estimated fabrication cost of the fuel assembly over its produced energy over depletion. For the MIX fuel, it is roughly proportional to the ratio between the U-235 fuel enrichment and the fuel cycle length. More information on this indicator can be find in [10]. MIX fuel compositions are constrained by the discharge burn-up, derived from the fuel cycle length with a 2.5 ratio (inherent to the 100 % MIX fuel management). A last quantity of interest used in this work is the void reactivity effect, here the margin to criticality in case of a complete loss of water in the core. It is evaluated via a surrogate model built from calculations at fuel assembly (FA) scale , for a given fuel isotopic composition, fuel depletion and void fraction [12][13]. Optimisation objectives and constraints are summarised in Table I.

Table I. Optimisation objectives and constraints.

Objectives	Peaking factor Fuel front-end cost	To minimise To minimise
Constraints	Discharge burn-up [MWd/t] Void reactivity effect (pcm)	$\in [49 ; 51]$ < -2000

The design of experiments is based on maximum entropy sampling [14]. More than 500 points are sampled via this method. Sampling range is given in Table II, based on [11]. Plutonium 238 fraction is use as the complementary to 100.

Table II. Design of interest ranges.

Input parameters	Range
U-235 fuel enrichment (%)	[0 ; 3.5]
Plutonium content (%)	[6 ; 10]
Pu-238 fraction (%)	[2.2 ; 5]
Pu-239 fraction (%)	[38 ; 56.9]
Pu-240 fraction (%)	[23.1 ; 33]
Pu-241 fraction (%)	[5 ; 10]
Pu-242 fraction (%)	[6.1 ; 19]
Am-241 fraction (%)	[0.5 ; 3]

Surrogate models are then trained on the design of experiments. Here, gaussian processes are retained for their unbiased estimator and the associated confident indicator. Gaussian processes building is done thanks to the *DiceKriging* package [15]. The surrogate model quality is assessed via a leave-one-out cross validation. Confidence intervals are evaluated under the assumption that the bias, or the prediction-measure error, follows a Gaussian distribution. Table III summarises confidence intervals for studied quantities of interest. When compared to the average of one quantity of interest, the surrogate model returns an estimation with a good to very good accuracy, below 2 %, depending on the studied quantity.

Table III. Confidence intervals for selected quantities of interest.

Quantities of interest	min.	avg.	max.	σ	3σ	$\sigma/\text{avg.}$
Fuel cycle length (MWd/t)	5 480	19 190	27 630	36	108	0.19 %
Peaking factor	1.462	1.501	1.589	0.004	0.012	0.3 %
Front-end cost	0.89	1.53	3.91	0.03	0.09	2 %

3. SCENARIO OF APPLICATION

The reference fuel cycle scenario simulated in this work is the trajectory “MIX 8 %” as detailed in [11] and illustrated in Figure 3.

With 15 MIX fully loaded EPR reactors combined with 23 LEU EPR reactors, it is possible to stabilise the plutonium inventory by the middle of the century. Depleted fuel reprocessing capacities, shown in Figure 4, need to be available in order to insure consistent MIX fuel reprocessing and plutonium separation. One can see how first depleted MOX fuel assemblies are reprocessed, then are depleted MIX fuel assemblies. MOX / MIX reprocessing capacities increase in two-steps, stabilising at 550 t/year around 2060 and after, while LEU reprocessing capacities slowly decrease over time, from 1050 t/year at the beginning of the simulation to 650 t/year at the end. The fine yellow band at the end of simulation represent ERU fuel reprocessing capacities, not discussed in this work.

In this MIX fuel cycle, the plutonium content is fixed at 8 % and the discharge burn-up is set at 50 GWd/t. To reach the targeted discharge burn-up, U-235 enrichment of the uranium support increases from 2 % to 3 % in 40 years, to balance the loss of plutonium fissile quality. For this study, the retained refuelling scheme is composed of 96 fresh FAs, with 96 second-cycle FAs and 48 third-cycle FAs, hence only half of the second-cycle FAs are kept for a third cycle. The refuelling scheme is shown in Figure 1b. This peculiar refuelling scheme ensures an as flat as possible power distribution for MIX fuel with a plutonium content of about 8 % and a U-235 enrichment of about 2 %, so is pertinent for the fuel cycle studied here.

Figure 3. Nuclear power plant deployment, by energy produced, fuel and design.

Figure 4. Reprocessing capacities, per fuel type and design.

Figure 5 illustrates how the 4 quantities of interest impacts fuel manufacturing, for two pivotal years of the simulation, 2055 and 2080. These two years represent respectively the early period and the late period of plutonium multirecycling in MIX fuel, and are representative of the plutonium isotopic composition at the beginning and at the end of plutonium multi-recycling.

Figure 5. Distribution of optimisation objectives and constraints around a given fuel composition, for two years of the scenario: 2055 and 2080.

For a given year, before the optimisation process shown in Figure 2, TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE returns a fuel composition, represented by a black diamond and quoted as the "reference solution" on Figure 5. Around this point are drawn the contour lines for: the fuel front-end cost in green, the void reactivity effect in black, the discharge burn-up in red, and the peaking factor in blue.

As seen in Table I the void reactivity effect, the peaking factor and the discharge burn-up are constraints to be respected, while the fuel front-end cost is one of the objective to minimise. To decrease the fuel

front-end cost, one can either increase the discharge burn-up or decrease the fuel enrichment in U-235. However, since the discharge burn-up only have a narrow band of acceptable values, here between 49 GWd/t and 51 GWd/t, to decrease the U-235 fuel enrichment increases the fuel plutonium content. The plutonium content increase is limited both by the peaking factor and the void reactivity effect. Finally, only a narrow band of fuel compositions is reachable because of these criteria, bounded by the two red lines plus the black one. The black arrow represent the direction to move forward in order to improve the MIX fuel performances while respecting the optimisation constraints. Over time fuel isotopic composition evolves, because of the multirecycling process. The right subfigure in Figure 5 illustrates this phenomenon, the multiple recycling resulting in a harder control of the plutonium fissile quality. This evolution of the fuel isotopic composition impacts the different quantities of interest. The most notably changes are for the discharge burn-up as well as the fuel front-end cost. It is no surprise, since the two are directly correlated. The band of discharge burn-up acceptable values drifts to fuel compositions with higher U-235 fuel enrichment, getting closer to the void reactivity effect limit. Because of the U-235 fuel enrichment increasing, fuel front-end cost increases too. Peaking factor becomes less constraining over time, where void reactivity effect is less impacted by plutonium isotopic changes than MIX fuel composition, as discussed in [10]. As a consequence, no further optimisation is easily achievable on the 2080 and afterward, as it will be seen in Section 4.

This approach to optimise the MIX fuel composition is then applied for the entirety of the scenario and discussed in the following section.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The introduced method highlighted two improvement paths for the trajectory discussed in [11]: a reduction of the peaking power at the beginning of the studied scenario and potential gains from the front-end cost point of view, where a decrease of it seems achievable, as illustrated in Figure 5. Optimisation method results are depicted in Figure 6. The aim of the optimisation work is to minimise the fuel front-end cost while respecting as best as possible the following criteria: a peaking power below 1.50, a void reactivity effect below -2000 pcm, and a discharge burn-up of 50 GWd/t.

To minimise the peaking power at the beginning of the simulation, from 2045 to 2052, the chaining method suggests the following changes: to lower the discharge burn-up from 50 GWd/t to 38.5 GWd/t and the plutonium content from 8 % to 6.90 %. It indeed reduces the peaking power from about 1.53 to about 1.50, but leads to a suboptimal situation, because it forces one to free the discharge burn-up constraint in order to drastically lower the MIX plutonium content, which subsequently increases the fuel front-end cost from about 1.05 to about 1.22. This raises one interesting point, that the retained fuel management seems to not be well suited to the MIX fuel composition at the beginning of plutonium multirecycling deployment, and that a different core loading pattern should be considered for the transition period. Introduction of different core loading patterns or coupling the method with core loading pattern optimisers, such as the one discussed in [16], with the different fuel compositions as inputs, can be ways of improvement.

To respect the 50 GWd/t discharge burn-up target and minimise the front-end cost, the method strongly push to increase MIX fuel plutonium content. However, this is mitigated by the void reactivity effect limit, as seen in Figure 5 and set here with a -2000 pcm margin. Therefore, the scenario is cut into three periods, each corresponding to a specific plutonium content: 8.90 %, 8.45 % and 8 %, instead of the initial 8 % proposed in the original work. This allows a fuel front end-cost reduction from 1.35 to 1.30 between 2053 and 2060, then from about 1.40 to about 1.37 from 2061 to 2070. After 2070, since plutonium content is in both scenarios set at 8 %, fuel front-end cost is the same.

Both scenarios stabilise the plutonium inventory around 2060. But, in the optimised scenario it stabilises at 650 t, instead of 630 t for the initial scenario. This 20 t plutonium increase can be explained by a slower deployment of MIX fuel at the beginning of the optimised scenario, due to the decrease of both the plutonium content and the discharge burn-up and subsequent shortening of the fuel cycle length.

Moreover, as it can be seen in the upper right subfigure in Figure 6, MIX fuel plutonium content is of 6.90 % at the start of plutonium multirecycling, due to the minimisation of the peaking factor (see the upper left subfigure). As discussed in [10], plutonium consumption in MIX fuel is correlated to its plutonium content. The plutonium consumption decreases at the beginning of its multirecycling and the slower deployment of MIX fuel leads to this overall plutonium inventory slight increase. Fuel processing capacities, shown in Figure 4, are kept the same between the initial and optimised cases for comparison's sake.

Figure 6. Evolution of the different quantities of interest in the two MIX scenarios.

5. CONCLUSION

An innovative chaining method between core and fuel cycle simulations, relying on gaussian processes surrogate models, is introduced in this work. From a initial scenario, the chaining method helps designing an optimised one, that considers cores aspects of the plutonium multi-recycling within the future French EPR fleet while maintaining the initial scenario goals, such as the plutonium inventory fast stabilisation. This new method highlighted new optimisation levers for fuel cycle simulations by introducing core calculations and associated quantities of interest in the design of fuel cycle, focusing on existing or close to maturity reactor designs. It shows how margins could be gained by increasing the MIX fuel plutonium content without affecting core performances and how the selected fuel management appears unoptimised for early MIX fuel deployment in EPR. It is both suited for consolidate existing fuel deployment strategies and to design new ones. The presented chaining method is not technology-bonded and can be expanded to any kind of reactor that is to be modelled in fuel simulation studies and opens new fields of interaction between core and fuel cycle simulations. By questioning the priority order between the fuel, the reactor and the cycle scale, this work shows how the ranking of these three scales can affect the final trajectory and how it is important to well established the priority order, especially in technology constrained and soon-to-be deployed simulations like the one studied in this paper.

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